

Agama aculeata Ground Agama

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© L. Kemp

Group: Reptile

Size: 18-25 cm (total body length)

Distribution:

Namibia, Botswana, Zimbabwe, South Africa, Mozambique, southern Angola, Zambia, Eswatini

Importance:

Agama aculeata is a widespread, common ground agama in southern Africa that helps control insects and thrives in natural and disturbed habitats. Sequencing its genome would resolve taxonomic uncertainty within the species complex, uncover genetics of coloration, thermal tolerance and urban adaptation, improve agama phylogeny, and aid conservation and monitoring.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 71.28 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 3.17 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 1.5 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.6% [Single: 98.4%, Duplicated: 1.2%]

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 1114.67 kilobases

Contig number: 10 320

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